

IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATION AND CONDUCT OF PRACTICAL TRAINING IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract: This article considers the issues of improving the organization and conduct of practical classes in general secondary schools. Practical classes play an important role in strengthening students' theoretical knowledge, developing critical and creative thinking skills. The study analyzes the planning of practical classes, the use of modern pedagogical technologies, methods for achieving active participation of students, and assessment mechanisms. Also, recommendations are given for the effective organization of practical classes for schoolchildren.

Keywords: practical classes, general secondary education, pedagogical technologies, assessment system, "Term chain", "Chain of confusion", alkali metals, calcium.

Introduction

Today, practical exercises play a significant role in the effective organization of the educational process in general secondary schools and in consolidating students' knowledge. Practical exercises help students connect theoretical knowledge with practice, develop independent thinking and creative approach skills. Therefore, improving the organization and conduct of these exercises is an important issue.

Main Section

The importance of practical exercises.

Practical exercises are an integral part of the educational process, which have the following advantages:

1. Strengthening theoretical knowledge.
2. Increasing student interest.
3. Developing independent problem-solving skills.
4. Developing teamwork skills.
5. Cultivating a scientific-experimental approach.

Methods of organizing practical exercises

1. Interdisciplinary approach - identifying the connection between several disciplines and applying them in real life;
2. Using educational technologies - using interactive methods, modern laboratory equipment and digital technologies;
3. Group and collective work - dividing students into groups and directing them to work together on a project;
4. Conducting experiments - developing the study of subjects through laboratory and practical work;
5. Problem-based learning - creating conditions for students to solve various problems;
6. Excursions and practical experiences - consolidating knowledge through familiarization with real-life objects.

Directions for improving practical training

1. Providing schools with modern laboratories and technical equipment.
2. Widely introducing interactive teaching methods.
3. Allocating more time to practical training.
4. Sending teachers to continuous professional development.
5. Strengthening an individual approach to students.
6. Improving the system for assessing practical training.

Examples of using educational technologies in organizing practical training: Practical work topic 2 in chemistry for grade 9 in the III quarter: Solving experimental problems on the topics “Alkali metals” and “Calcium”. We will consolidate the topics using the “Term chain” method.

Pair the number of terms with their definition.

1	NaOH	A	It is used to reduce soil acidity.
2	Li	B	Caustic soda
3	NaHCO ₃	D	Used in photography.
4	CaCO ₃	E	Drinking soda
5	Mg	F	Metal with stimulating properties.

The answers are summarized as follows: 1-B, 2-F, 3-E, 4-A, 5-D.

The topic of practical work 3 in chemistry for grade 9 in the fourth quarter: Solving experimental problems on the topic of “Metals”. The “Confused Chain” method was chosen for this topic.

The metals given in confusion are grouped according to their properties. To encourage students to be resourceful, non-metals are also added to the list of metals:

Fe, Li, Ne, Ni, K, Si, W, Hg, Mo, Al, Cu, Br, He.

Light metals	Heavy metals	Non-ferrous metals	Rare metals

➤ The correct answer is:

Light metals	Heavy metals	Non-ferrous metals	Rare metals
Li, K, Al	Fe, Ni, Hg, Mo, W	Ni, Cu, Al	Mo, W

Conclusion

Improving the organization and conduct of practical training in general secondary schools will greatly contribute to improving the quality of education. Practical training is important in strengthening students' theoretical knowledge, teaching them to apply it in life, and developing their ability to think independently. Therefore, to further improve this process, it is necessary to effectively use advanced methods and modern technologies.

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